

METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING NATURAL SCIENCES LESSONS IN PRIMARY CLASSES ON THE BASIS OF THE 4K MODEL.

Esonova is the daughter of Ruzigul Ilhom

Master's student of Termiz University of Economics and Service, majoring in
theory and methodology of education and training (primary education)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14201858>

Abstract: This article provides detailed information about the effectiveness of interactive teaching of natural sciences using modern methods and new technologies based on the "4K" model.

Keywords: Natural sciences, primary class, 4K model, education, modern methods, interactivity, Creativity, Communicative, Critical, Collaboration, effective thinking, innovative methods, international, Asia, Singapore, South Korea.

The development of the society is largely determined by the intellectual potential of the state. Because the leadership of our country is paying great attention to the fundamental reform of the education system. Accordingly, training of highly qualified personnel is rising to the level of state policy. We consider the specific requirements of organizing and managing educational processes to achieve the training of highly qualified specialists. First of all, primary education is considered the most important stage of personality formation.

This period is not only the period of the first restoration of the foundation of children's imagination and knowledge, but also the understanding of the subconscious world of the child requires very careful attention, and the child "creates the personality of the student" in himself. their enthusiasm increases, and they step by step in the path of science in order to achieve high results As a permanent and complex problem, an important approach to the ideological and educational aspects of textbooks is envisaged.

In the concept of development of the public education system in our country until 2030, the task of improving the teaching methodology has been set. In particular, on the basis of advanced foreign experiences, textbooks of the 1st-4th grade were newly prepared on the basis of the "4K" model. The use of the "4K" model is a tried-and-tested, most importantly, modern approach. Previously, we paid more attention to children's writing and wrote many diktats for them. With the new experience, students' critical thinking and the ability to freely express their opinion are given more importance.

These new modern school textbooks provide an innovative approach, this

methodology is aimed at the comprehensive development of children.

The "4K" model includes four core competencies Collaborative textbooks are designed to help students develop teamwork skills. It helps students learn the skills of collaboration, effective communication, and mutual support.

Communicative (communication skills) textbooks are aimed at developing students' ability to communicate with others. Students learn to express their thoughts clearly and clearly, to listen and understand the interlocutor, and to effectively use language tools in conveying information.

Critical (critical) thinking is a methodology that includes the development of students' skills to critically evaluate information, to form their own opinions and judgments. Students learn to approach their problems from an analytical point of view and form their own point of view based on logical thinking.

Creative thinking (creative approach) textbooks develop creative thinking and creativity. Students learn to use new approaches to achieve their goals, develop innovative solutions, and gain creative problem-solving skills. [1.211]

Deputy of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis: U. Jabbarov "New modern textbooks for primary classes will help to comprehensively develop the young generation, the owners of our future, and successfully adapt to modern society "It becomes even more important because it is aimed at forming the necessary skills in them." [2.2]

Accordingly, we can say that our modern textbooks are a boon for us. That is, to teach our children to effectively exchange ideas, to support each other, to express their thoughts clearly and clearly, to listen and understand the interlocutor, to be able to effectively use language tools to convey information, to approach problems from an analytical point of view, based on logical thinking to form one's own point of view, to be able to use new approaches to achieve one's goals. they will have the skills to develop innovative solutions and solve creative problems.

These "4K" skills are of great importance in both physical and mental development of children in improving a healthy lifestyle, inclusive educational environment. Learning about art, science, sports, or the natural world increases children's outlook and self-confidence. Each lesson at school not only helps students master the content of science, but also develops independent learning, analytical thinking, problem solving and coping skills. Elementary school textbooks are aimed at forming the skills necessary for the comprehensive development of the young generation and the preparation of mature specialists for society.

Natural-scientific in elementary school students with natural sciences education. The mutual integration of sciences in the formation of technical, ecological and economic literacy and the development of critical and creative thinking lays the groundwork for the understanding of nature by the object as a whole being, and the creation of a single natural-scientific view of the world in their thinking. Also, through this science, students can understand the opportunities and problems of interdisciplinary integration of modern science and technology development, understand the nature of environmental problems through the goals of sustainable development education, and learn from nature. Aimed at forming the ways of rational use, the principles of following a healthy lifestyle, and the skills of using the acquired knowledge in everyday life.

Natural sciences teach students about the causes and interrelationships of phenomena and processes occurring in animate and inanimate nature, the stages of development in nature, including the evolution of the development of living organisms, the natural-scientific foundations of modern techniques and technology, nature and helps to learn about the interconnectedness and influence of society, the scientific basis of the economical use of natural resources, and the importance of a healthy lifestyle. The student's internal motivation, through his interest in mastering natural sciences, plays an important role in understanding the state of the natural and social environment, understanding environmental and human problems, and being able to make decisions to find their solutions.

The weather can be different in different parts of our planet at the same time. For example: in Central Asia, as the air warms up, the pressure decreases, as a result, cooler air masses enter here from the north-northwest and slightly lower the temperature of the area. As a result of weather changes, air masses are exchanged. The sun does not heat and cool the globe uniformly, so the condition of the air is not the same everywhere. [3.194]

Elementary school students can easily understand this by observing their surroundings. Simply put, they know that it will be cold in the morning, warm in the afternoon, and cold again in the dark. Students' natural-scientific literacy in solving a problem situation. They are required to demonstrate "4K" skills. The students' cognitive attitude (interest in natural sciences, scientific approach to the researched issue, awareness of issues related to the environment, and knowledge of the content of science determined their literacy in natural sciences. During the study of natural sciences, students are motivated. According to this, the following three countries are leading among the advanced countries

that use new educational technologies in practice: Estonia. Singapore and South Korea. [5.2]

Estonia. Estonian schoolchildren today regularly use the services of e-Schoolbag and Opiq, which provide electronic learning materials. They have the opportunity to learn about robotics through Roboversity. And parents can always monitor their children's learning and communicate with teachers on the special eKool platform [5.3]

Singapore. In the early 1990s, Singapore's Ministry of Education began to modernize its education system. In the conditions of this knowledge economy, Singapore took the first steps in the direction of preparing the school for life: for the first time, the curriculum of high schools and colleges included "Computer lessons". and tell about the importance of active use of technologies for the development of the country's economy [5.3]

Key areas such as the development of new requirements for the 21st century were included. Gradually students and the technique they use the ratio of tools was brought to 1:1. New technologies began to be accepted as a means of providing education to everyone, regardless of where they live: this was an important factor in the emergence of the idea of "lifelong learning" Since 2015, the main emphasis in Singapore's education has been on "creative teaching": teachers, as designers of educational environments, have begun to conduct classes using new technologies. It also adapted the learning process to individual learning, students had the opportunity to study anywhere and at any time.

South Korea. The process of introducing new technologies into South Korea's education system began in the 80s. At this time, many negative world changes (population aging, youth unemployment, etc.) gave the country's government the idea of introducing rapid innovations into the national education system. The general increase in the competitiveness of Korean education and science was one of the important directions of the country's development. The use of ICT in schools was considered as a means to achieve the set goals. The program focuses on the development of distance education, which expands access to education for all aspirants, to acquire new skills and knowledge, or to learn missed activities. [5.4]

In lessons, teachers use various multimedia materials. communicate with students. And in remote classes, the teacher uses specially developed educational materials, creates a creative environment and evaluates knowledge. During education, a special trainer (tutor) is also attached, who monitors the learning process of students, helps teachers to work with virtual and cloud

technologies. In recent years, virtual schools and universities have been actively increasing in South Korea.

The educational process in them is completely online education with the help of tools, and students take the courses they are interested in according to the curriculum created within their interests (for example, Air and Correspondence High School; Ewha Womans University, Hanyang Cyber University and International Cyber University). In short, the use of new technologies at school not only makes the educational process colorful and interesting, but also allows children to develop computer literacy and other important innovations of the 21st century.

Quality and competitive education is the guarantee of success in sustainable economic growth, development of science and technology, and improvement of the quality of social services. Don't be afraid of new technologies. Effective use of them, absorbing foreign experience and drawing conclusions from mistakes, will bring us great achievements. I believe that this will be our greatest achievement when our future children grow up with their own free thoughts and life views.

References:

1. Sangirova Z. B // The importance of the "4K" model in the development of natural-scientific literacy in students. // 25.10.2023
2. U. Jabbarov. // "4K" model in the primary class - an innovative approach to modern education. // Aniq.uz
3. D. Sharipova, D. P. Khodiyeva, M. K. Shirinov // Teaching of natural science methodology // T. 2018
4. B. Holvigitova // Creative abilities of primary school students Tasks on formation by means of fiction // Science and innovation scientific and practical conference // Innovative Academy, 2023
5. T. Naushirvanov // Digitization of education // Khan Academy Uzbek Blog // 06.11.2019

